

NEMO DAT QUOD NON HABET: THE LEGALITY OF THE 1913 AGREEMENTS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR JUDGMENT BASED THEREON IN THE CAMEROON-NIGERIA BORDER DISPUTE

¹Utobo, Onele Joseph; ²Onuoha, J.I and ³Nwanolue, B.O.G. (MON)

¹ Ph.D (Law); Ph.D (Pol.Sc); MSc (Public Admin); BA (Ed.); BL.

Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Law, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki

²Professor of Political Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

³Professor of Political Science, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbarian, Anambra State, Nigeria.

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Keywords: <i>Border Dispute, Treaty of Protection; Effectivite; Bakassi Peninsula; Cession; Cameroon; Nigeria; Equatorial Guinea; International Court of Justice; Eurocentrism.</i>	Abstract: <i>Dissatisfaction and disaffection have persisted in the Bight of Biafra following the widely alleged miscarriage of justice in the Cameroon-Nigeria border dispute, especially as it concerned the Bakassi Peninsula. Thus, the legality of the 1913 Agreements and the judgment founded thereon in the said dispute has remained a source of concern to critical minds in jurisprudence, international law and politics. Therefore, the objectives of the study included, to identify the legal interpretation of a protectorate; to describe the tenor of 1884 Treaty of Protection; to ascertain the cause of the Cameroon-Nigeria boundary dispute and contention over ownership of the Bakassi Peninsula in particular; to verify the validity of the 1913 Agreements and their implications for the International Court of Justice's (ICJ) judgment based thereon. As a doctrinal research, we relied only on statutory and judicial authorities and other secondary materials for our data, which, as it should, were content analyzed. The results of our analysis included that a protectorate is neither a colony nor did they said 1884 Treaty create one, so that any agreement, including especially the 1913 Agreements, contrary to that tenor, or judgment based thereon, were illegal and invalid. Among others, were recommended that unilateral alteration of treaties by parties thereto, under any guise, should not be allowed; that Article 61 of the ICJ Statute, among others, should be amended to re-open the revision window to enable Nigeria apply for the reversal or over-ruling of the award of the Bakassi Peninsula to Cameroon based on the ultra vires 1913 Agreements. Also, the parties should resort to diplomatic options in resolving their border dispute in order to ensure enduring peace, security and wellbeing in the region.</i>
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INTRODUCTION

Africa's contact with Europe in the second half of the 19th century was a child of necessity. It arose from the latter's industrial revolution between the 18th and 19th centuries and need for external markets for the excess manufactured goods. On the heels of this was the need for spheres of control and territorial acquisition. This necessitated Euro-African treaties between the African nations and the European powers. The ethnic conflicts and struggles for territories that came with this new contact was so alien to Africa that the traditional rulers had to seek European powers' protection against stronger adversaries.

Surreptitiously, these European powers converted this guardianship into colonization. They so recklessly and unclearly demarcated or redefined traditional boundaries, slicing apart homogenous groups and lumping together heterogeneous ones, according to Wole Soyinka, "...like some demented tailor who paid no attention to the fabric, colour or pattern of the quilt he was patching together" (Dakas, 2003, p. 29). The consequent boundary conflicts turned the once quiet continent, according to Nwogwugwu (2014, p.17) into "... a theatre of war," requiring treaties of protection by the weak against the strong. This led to the 1884 Treaty of Protection between the Queen of Britain and the Kings and Chiefs of Old Calabar. The contestations surrounding the interpretation of the tenor of this 1884 Treaty informed our application, in this study, of the theory of constructivism. Traced to Kant, Hegel, Descartes and Marx (Burrett & Morgan, 1985),

constructivism was given its modern appeal by the works of Edmund Hesserl (1859-1938). It is concerned with the substantive analysis of international relations (Walker, 1989) as a "divided discipline" of theoretical disagreements (Agara, 2016, p.3). This is especially since the post-cold War paradigm shift from realism. It studies the dynamics in the construction of relations, laws and treaties among international actors.

The relevance of this theory to our present study includes that it views human and states relations as an interactive process of shared ideas leading to structures in form of treaties, laws or agreements which regulate the actors' conducts. Accordingly, even if the International Court of Justice (ICJ) refuses, or not allowed by law, to reverse its decision on the Cameroon-Nigeria border dispute, especially as it affects the Bakassi Peninsula, both states and their affected populations could, through constructivist social interactions, rationalize their ideas, interests and values for purposes of international peace and regional development.

To expound on this intricate topic, this study, which is largely limited to the Bakassi Peninsula as the most contentious in this border dispute, sought to answer the following research questions: What is the legal interpretation of a protectorate?; What brought contention over the ownership of the Bakassi Peninsula in particular and boundary dispute between Nigeria and Cameroon in general?; How valid are the 1913 Agreements that altered the 1884 Treaty?; and what is the implication of the 1913 Agreements for the ICJ judgment based thereon

in the Cameroon-Nigeria boundary dispute? These shall form the various sections of the study.

Section 1: The Protectorate System: Origin and Implications.

Protectorate system is an administrative contrivance, a child of necessity, to forestall what Kautilya, in his *Arthashastra*, call 'law of fish,' where the larger or stronger swallowed the smaller or weaker (Appadorai, 2003, p.20). This system is traceable to the Mid-17th Century British history when Oliver Cromwell, as Lord Protector (1653-1658), succeeded by his son, Richard Cromwell, governed England from 1653 to 1659. It is a protective system, developed by the Cromwells as a government by a protector, stronger state over an underdeveloped, protected, weaker state, for defense from external enemies, but without amounting to direct annexation or legal status of a colony (Lorimer & Lechner, eds; 2000, p.803).

Protectorate relationship is recognized in international law as arising when a weaker nation transfers control over its foreign affairs, or "...the management of its more important international affairs to the stronger nation" (Garner, ed; 2004, p. 1260), in exchange for the protection. However, as such weaker states are often under the protection of an imperialist power, the relationship, though not directly colonial, has, albeit unlawfully, often approximated an annexation. For example, the relationship between the South Pacific islands and Great Britain since 1889 (McLean & McMillan, 2003).

Thus, the practice of protectorate system was commonly used by European powers to expand their empires in the underdeveloped worlds, especially in Africa, Asia and Latin America, up to even 20th Century. For example, Nigeria up to 1945 under Britain, and Puerto Rico and Guam under the United States as currently unincorporated territories. However, by protectorate arrangement, the protected state retains some extent of autonomy over internal affairs while the protector controls its foreign policy, including especially defence. Although the practice is no longer fashionable in modern times, unless among UN trust or mandate territories due to prioritization of independence, and sovereignty egoism among states, it still exists in such similar forms as international or transitional, mandate administrations pending self-governance.

Besides, what informs contemporary debates about the persistence, or subsistence, of protectorate practice is the exigency for protection above any egoism, as the latter could hardly be sustained without the former. The protection is expressed, in modern times, rather than governance, in the form of peacekeeping operations or humanitarian intervention, nonetheless, with critical scrutiny by world bodies, especially the UN pursuant to its commitment to equality of all nations, large and small (Preamble to the UN Charter).

As it should, a protection treaty, without more, surmises preservation or guardianship of the res rather than its abolition, obliteration, cession, conversion or transfer, unless otherwise clearly provided. Accordingly, Oppenheim (Dakas,

2003, pp.198 -9) describe a protectorate treaty as:

As an arrangement ... entered into whereby one state, while retaining to some extent its separate identity as a state, is subject to a kind of guardianship of another state. The ... consequences ... depend upon the particular provisions of ... the treaty of protection which enumerates the reciprocal rights and duties of the protecting and the protected states ... But it is characteristic of a protectorate that the protected state always has, and retains for some purposes, a position of its own as an international person and a subject of international law.

Section 2: The 1884 Protectorate Treaty and Tenor of a Protectorate Treaty.

The practice of European treaties with Africa dates back to pre-colonial times (See Table 1 below), ultimately for economic and imperialistic goals. Britain was not alone in this imperial expansionism. There were others, including Belgium, France, Germany, Portugal and Spain. Their struggle for external markets, or spheres of control, following the Industrial Revolution in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, led to the scramble for Africa (Mazrui, 1993). Britain and Germany had the largest presence in this West Coast region. However, the former had by 1849, in order to counter the 1847 French treaty of friendship, established a consulate for the Bight of Benin, former Bight of

Biafra, with headquarters in Fernando Po, principally for the protection of her traders (Nwabueze, 1983).

Thus, the immediate cause of the need for treaty of protection in this region was the bloody dispute between Prince Archibong and the Eyambas. In order to prevent the weaker Eyambas from securing German protection, which could give the latter right over Old Calabar, King Eyo VII and Duke IX entered into the 23 July and 10 September 1884 treaties with Britain for protection. Although the latter was more comprehensive, none of the two treaties was signed until the 1st World War broke out in 1914 and ultimately aborted them. However, before the war, ascendancy rivalry between Britain and Germany had, by 1889, led to several raids by the latter of Efik traders, including taking King Eyo VII prisoner.

Indeed, by 1891, Germany had assumed sovereignty over Old Calabar, extensively dislodging Britain and terminated her commercial hegemony therein. The era was greeted with series of Anglo –German negotiations and exchanges of notes for avoidance of escalations that could have led to a world war earlier than 1914. These pacts include those of 29 April and 7 May, 1885; 27 July and 2 August, 1886; 15 November, 1893; 19 March, 1906; and the ultimate 11 March and 12 April, 1913 Agreements, all based on the 1884 Treaty.

Table 1: Pre-colonial/Colonial Treaties Protection in Bakassi Peninsula

Year	Character of Treaty	Treaty Partners	Content
1841	Anti-Slavery	British-Efik at Old Calabar	To stop slave trade and embrace legitimate trade.
1842	Enforcement of Anti-Slavery Activities	British and Efiks	To empower Britain to intervene on slavery matters with force.
1842	Friendship and Protection	French and King of Duala, Kamerum (Cameroun)	Part of Cameroon sought to remain under Britain rule and Eastern Nigeria.
1881	Annexation	British and Efiks	Annexation of territory from Bini (Benin) to Cameroon to preclude French territorial ambition.
1884	Balkanisation of African (Berlin Conference)	British and Germans	Deciding on colonial borders and claims, and making Rio Del Rey estuary as accepted ethnic frontier between Nigeria and Cameroon on the Peninsula to forestall territorial conflict of ownership.
1913	Sovereignty over Bakassi Peninsula	British and Germans	Defined land and maritime boundary by relying on Rio Del Rey as accepted frontier on the Peninsula.
1913	Henderson Fleurian Exchange of Notes on Sovereignty of Bakassi	British and French	Setting out conditions for British continued retention of Bakassi area as part of Eastern Nigeria.

Source: Etekpe, 2013, p. 288.

2.1: Tenor of a Protectorate Treaty.

The 1884 Treaty is one of such Euro-packaged treaties with African societies. This time, it was on request from the Obong of Calabar in “a letter to the British Government to send a man of war to come and protect him because the Germans have brought down a Union Jack in front of his

house and beaten his boys and broken their heads” (Eze, et al; 2012, p.3). Such treaties of protection were couched tactically to remove resistance or resentment among the native African Kings. For example, Article 1 of the 1884 Treaty aptly provides:

Article 1: Her Majesty, the Queen of Great Britain and Ireland ... in compliance with the request of the Kings, Chiefs and people of Old Calabar, hereby undertakes to extend to them, and to the territory under their authority and jurisdiction, her gracious favour and protection. Although such treaties purport that the territories were “... not within the British dominion but... under the exclusive control of the King, its government cannot hold direct communications with any foreign power, (and vice versa) ... without the prior approval of the British Government” (Egwummuo, 1998, p.10; Dakas, 2003, p.63; Parenthesis ours). Thus, they actually limit, or even oust, the powers of the African King. For example, Article 2 of the 1884 Treaty provides:

Article 2: The Kings and Chiefs of Old Calabar agree and promise to refrain from entering into any Correspondence, Agreement or Treaty with any foreign nation or power, except with the knowledge and sanction of Her Britannic Majesty’s Government.

Notwithstanding the common control of the foreign affairs of a protected state by the protecting state, it has been held in a number of cases, including *R v Crewe (1910) 2 KB 603-4*, that a treaty of protection creates “... dominion in the sense of power and jurisdiction ... not... dominion in the sense of territorial dominion,” nor loss of sovereignty as captured in the above Article 2. The subsisting status was aptly noted by Oppenheim that “... it is characteristic of a protectorate that the protected state always has, and retains, for some purposes, a position of its own as an international person and a subject of

international law.” To do the contrary by any of the parties to a protectorate treaty would amount to unilateral alteration and violation of the customary international law principle of *pacta sunt servanda*, that is, the obligation to respect agreement by parties thereto.

As it is, any treatment of a protectorate by the protecting state, either by way of cession, transfer, etc, unless otherwise expressly provided, or in violation of the rights of property of the natives is *ultra vires* a treaty of protection. See the view of Viscount Heldene in *Amodu Tijani v Secretary, Southern Province (1921) 3 NLR 55*, that any treatment of the protected territory must be “...made on the footing that the rights of property of the inhabitants were to be respected...” Similarly, it was held in *AG Southern Nigeria v John Holt Ltd & Anor (1910) 2 NLR 1 at 4; (1915) AC 599*, inter alia, “... that all rights of property existing in the inhabitants under grant or otherwise from King Docemo and his predecessors were to be respected.”

Therefore, the 1884 Treaty, like any other of protection, neither created an annexation, alienation, nor a cession, other than a protectorate which, as always characteristic, is for no more than “... a kind of guardianship by another state” (Dakas, 2003, p.198). Furthermore, as the rulers had mere equitable rights as trustees over territory under their authority or jurisdiction, such grants, other than a protectorate, cannot stand because such rulers, on grounds of the hackneyed principle of *nemo dat quod non habet*, would not convey title superior to the one they possessed. Accordingly, a protectorate treaty gives only “...

an inchoate title to territory...” (Brown, nd; p. 254) and, as held in the *Ethiopia-Somaliland Frontier Dispute*, involves no transfer of territory.

Finally, contemporaneous with the 1884 Treaty, the British Foreign Office (BFO), at the 1885 Berlin Conference, stated that, without prejudice to the right of the aborigines:

... A protectorate involves not the direct assumption of territorial sovereignty but... assumption of territorial rights (not ownership or transference of power)... necessary to maintain the paramount authority and discharge the duties of the protecting power (Shaw, 1986, p. 283, n.155; Utobo, 2021, p.177; Parenthesis ours).

Section 3: The 1913 Agreements.

As can be seen in Table 2 below, these agreements of 11 March and 12 April, 1913, adjusted the boundary set under the 1884 Treaty from Rio del Rey to Akwa Yafe (See Table 1 above). This adjustment, besides British quest for access to Calabar, arose from German discontent with the boundary demarcation under the 1884 Treaty. It crashed on the indistinct demarcations there under and, via the 1913 instrument, had to neutralize British title over the Rio del Rey, otherwise called Bakassi. Although Britain claimed to competently act under the 1890 Foreign Jurisdiction Act (FJA), which empowers it to treat a protectorate as a colony, ceded or conquered territory, it acted *ultra vires* the 1884 Treaty. And, having not been empowered by the latter, the 1913 Agreements are unsupportable and void *ab initio*.

Thus, even though the 1913 Agreements are widely touted as “... the most significant of the various agreements between the two powers...” (Ariye, 2015, p.26), it was neither signed/enforceable even after the 1st World War, nor could Britain validly convey the Bakassi Peninsula under it in exchange for its “access to Calabar which is its key trading port” (Baye, 2011, pp. 19, 20), or for any other reason. In fact, the German Ambassador to Britain (1912 -14), Prince Karl Max Linosky, recorded, in respect of the 1913 Agreements, that “the Treaty became a casualty of the First World War,” as it could not be signed after all.

Accordingly, this still-born instrument cannot validly affect the Nigeria-Cameroon boundary. Thus, both the retention of the 1913 border, and the 1954 British Secretary of State for the Colonies’ legal order placing the Bakassi in the Southern Cameron, as noted by Etekpe (2013), among others Europeans trades on interests, *ultra vires* the 1884 Treaty, are erroneous and cannot be sustained in law, as the basis they could be established does not exist. In fact, aside the abortion of the 1913 Agreements by the 1st World War, including the November 22, 1913 Order-in-Council (in force 1 January, 1914) amalgamating the North and South Protectorates of Nigeria, Britain had within months of making these agreements denounced them as “... not treaty in force” (Mbuluh, 2004, p.11: Akinjide, 1994). It is, therefore, not tedious to conclude that Nigeria-Cameroon boundary remained as it is under the 1884 Treaty, and not validly adjusted by the 1913 Agreements as purported.

Table 2: The 1913 Agreements.

Date	Place of Treaty	of Treaty Partners	Content:
11 March, 1913	London	Britain & Germany	Settled the frontier between the two powers, from Yola in the North to the sea; and regulating the navigation on the Cross River.
12 April, 1913	Obokun, Cross River, Nigeria.	Britain & Germany	Confirmed the precise demarcation of the Anglo-German boundary between Nigeria and Cameroon from Yola to the Cross River and the Bight of Biafra.

Source: Utobo, 2025; Culled from Mbuluh, 2004, p.6

Section 4: Cameroon-Nigeria Border Dispute

The Cameroon-Nigeria boundary dispute centers primarily over ownership of the Bakassi Peninsula. Cameroon’s claim was only later extended to run her entire boundary with Nigeria. Both countries are West African neighbours that share border, stretching from the Lake Chad to the Gulf of Guinea and the sea (Brownlie, 1985). Besides that “... boundaries have significant considerations on the political, economic and social development and existence of the modern state,” (per Lord Curzon, cited in Utobo, 2017, p. 14), the strategic location and security relevance to both Nigeria and Cameroon of Bakassi Peninsula, and the oil and marine wealth bellied under it, instigated both countries’ interest in an area hitherto derided as “the flat, swampy and unhealthy Cameroons” (Weladji, 1975, pp. 165-6). Thus, for Nigeria, loss of Bakassi amounted to loss of its eastern access to the Atlantic Ocean and to the Bay of Calabar, and consequently blocked from international waters or her naval ships’ access to

South Africa except with the leave of Cameroon. On the other hand, for Cameroon, losing the Bakassi Peninsula meant being bordered by Sea, yet without access to international waters and, therefore, it wanted to possess Bakassi’s ownership at all cost (Familugba & Ojo, 2013). These security (soft or hard) (Elaigwu, 1996) reasons make ownership contention over the Bakassi Peninsula in the border dispute peculiar and zero-sum (Utobo, 2021). But to avoid the US/Canada boundary dispute ‘ Oregon Question’ saga which defied bilateral solutions, or possible resort to full blown war, in the face of obvious Nigeria’s military advantage, Cameroon, on 29 March, 1994, marched to the ICJ, at the Hague, questioning sovereignty over Bakassi.

This action was brought under forum *prorogatum*, as there was no special agreement or *compromis* between both parties, even as Nigeria lobbied for bilateral negotiation. But President Paul Biya of Cameroon concealed his apprehension about the strategic station of Bakassi, to his country’s economy and security,

under his revulsion for the “... humiliation by General Sani Abacha” via the 1st January, 1994 Nigeria’s military action (Obasanjo 2014, p. 281). Both parties braced for the litigation except the Equatorial Guinea which merely applied to intervene, in line with Article 62 of the ICJ Statute, neither as “... a party to the case,” nor take steps adverse to any of the parties. It merely sought to apprise the court of how its decision, in view of the parties’ claims, could affect her interest, especially the Bioko Island where its capital, Malabo, is located.

In its judgment, delivered on 10 October, 2002, the ICJ awarded ownership and sovereignty over the Bakassi Peninsula to Cameroon, purportedly in accordance with international law, citing the *Paquette Habana* case (175 US 677), followed in the *Charming Betsy* case (1804) 2 Cranch 64 at 118. Although the court considered other instruments, including the League of Nations Mandate Agreements, the UN Trusteeship Agreement, the Yaounde I and II Declarations, the 1946 Order-in-Council, the Kano Agreement and the Maroua Declaration tendered before it, the award was primarily based on the 1913 Anglo-German Agreements. The court held that the latter “... acquired validity on the strength of Foreign Jurisdiction Act of 1890 “(Anyu, 2007, p. 50), a unilateral/domestic British law.

The Court rejected Nigeria’s argument based on the *nemo dat quod non habet* principle, or that the 1884 Treaty created a protectorate to protect, rather than to alienate, their lands. It also rejected Articles XVIII – XXII of the 1913 Agreements which vest Nigeria with “... an

original title that considers it to be earlier in time and, therefore, superior to Cameroon’s claims” (Anyu, 2007, p. 49) based on long occupation, among other *effectivites*. It rather held that the 1890 Act empowered Britain to exercise its jurisdiction over its protectorate, however acquired, in as ample a manner indistinguishable from territories acquired by cession or conquest.

In the final analysis, the court held that the people of Old Calabar and Bakassi were rather colonies and vassal states under Britain’s suzerainty, wherefore the 1884 Treaty ceased to be an agreement between equal parties but “... rather a form of internal organization of colonial territory on the basis of autonomy for the natives...” (Anyu, 2007, p. 49). It concludes that, by the purport of the 1890 Act, the title of the people of Old Calabar over the Bakassi was not superior to that of Great Britain “... regardless of how valid or how old the title, and how clear the display of their sovereignty and degree of organization” (Anyu, *ibid*).

Section 5: Implications of the 1913 Agreements for the ICJ Judgment Based Thereon.

As it should, both Cameroon and Nigeria executed the Optional Clause in line with Article 36(2) of the ICJ Statute, thereby founding and accepting its jurisdiction, and its decision as binding. However, with due respect, we feel strongly about the World Court apparently eurocentrically arrogating to Britain, via the FJA 1890, the power of unilateral alteration of its treaty obligation, to wit, to protect the local indigenes and their property, thereby violating

same. Accordingly, the FJA, sanctified by the ICJ, has led a successful palace coup against the protectorate system, transforming it from a form of guardianship, *sans* ownership or dominion, to “an instrument of colonialism (Dakas, 2003, p. 219). This is surreptitious and inequitable.

Indeed, it is strange to hold, as the ICJ did, that Cameroon’s title, which purportedly arose from a treaty is superior to Nigeria’s which evolved from undisputed earlier and effectively continuous occupation since 1450s. The absurdity of that holding is based on the fact that treaties or agreements only vest derivative root of title while original title is only acquired by effective occupation of a *terra nullius*, except such original title is donated by the indigenous populations (Utobo, 2021, p. 166, n.84).

Thus, whatever the actions or omissions, goofs or unguarded statements emanating from Nigerians official and legal experts that facilitated the award of Bakassi Peninsula to Cameroon (Utobo, 2021, pp. 170 – 2; Ofonagoro, 2012 b; Dakas, 2003, pp. 107 – 9), the question remains: whether the ICJ was right in law to rely on the 1913 Agreements which, without doubt, is *ultra vires* the tenor of the 1884 Treaty of Protection it is claimed to emanate from? The latter, other than protection or guardianship, empowered neither Great Britani nor Germany to transfer or cede the territory of Old Calabar or other territories under its authority and jurisdiction, or any part thereof, including the Bakassi Peninsula.

The answer to the above question is, therefore, a loud and irrefutable NO! See the cases of *Island*

of Palmas (supra); R v Crewe (supra); Ethiopia-Somaliland Frontier Dispute (supra), etc, all of which uphold the *nemo dat* principle, thereby making the 1913 Agreement opposable, unsupported and illegal. Also, the 1885 BFO recognized the rights of the aborigines. But the court’s surrealistic interpretation of the 1884 Treaty, obsessed with eurocentrism, blurred its appreciation of Article 6 of the General Act of the Berlin Conference. The latter enjoined the European Powers “to watch out over the preservation of the native tribes and not to take over or effect transfer of their territory... (Or) native population from one administration to another without their consent...” (Judge Ajibola, para 206, Judgment 2002; parenthesis ours).

Accordingly therefore, the ICJ judgment on the Cameroon-Nigeria border dispute in general, and ownership of the Bakassi Peninsula is particular, based on the 1913 Agreements, on the same footing of the *nemo dat* principle, cannot stand because the agreements have no legal basis. They were made beyond and in violation of the tenor or ambit of their root - the 1884 Treaty of Protection. The judgments, although no more appealable, first because of the apex nature of the court, and second due to the expiry of the review window under Article 61 of the ICJ Statute, nonetheless remains poor and erroneous for illegal basis: the 1913 Agreements.

Section 6: Recommendations and Conclusion.

It has been found in the above study, inter alia, that a protectorate system, including the 1884 Treaty, creates a guardianship and requisite powers to carry same out rather than

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transference of territorial rights and powers of the natives. It was also found that the boundary dispute between Cameroon and Nigeria arose from European Powers' reckless and imprecise demarcation of African states traditional boundaries, the Anglo-German boundary adjustment under the 1913 Agreements and the discovery of enormous marine and oil wealth in Bakassi which originated Cameroon and Nigeria's life-and-death interest in the formerly loathed and despised peninsula.

Furthermore, we found that the 1913 Agreements, however significant it was held by the ICJ of the various agreements between the two powers (Britain and Germany) or superseding (Eke & Eke, 2007), were neither signed nor in force, and inherently *ultra vires* the 1884 Treaty which its purported validity and origin depended on. Therefore, the ICJ judgment founded thereon is not only reached *per incuriam* but also a Eurocentric conspiracy which, on grounds of the *nemo dat* principle, should not stand or pass for a precedent. Indeed, we are persuaded to hold that it is 'Not Yet Uhuru' for enduring peace and good neighbourliness, security and development in the West Coast region between Nigeria and Cameroon until the conspiratorial miscarriage of justice by the ICJ is reversed and the rights of Bakassians to their land restored.

Accordingly, we recommend, among others, that the international law rule of *pacta sunt servanda*, that is, respect for agreements, and should be held sacrosanct in international relations and politics. Unilateral alteration of treaties by any of the parties thereto, under any

guise, should not be allowed to stand. Such violation should, *prima facie*, ground a nullification of actions or benefits thereunder. Also, although there should be end to litigation, Article 61 of the ICJ Statute, among others, should be amended to keep open the window for revision of the court's judgment as long as there remain dissatisfaction and disaffection arising therefrom, and possibly the court to reverse itself where decision, as in the Cameroon-Nigeria border dispute, is capable of setting a bizarre precedent. Finally, the ICJ and the international community should encourage both countries to resolve their running alienation in other ways that promote healthy diplomatic relations, security in the region and welfare of the affected populations, since its decision cannot be validly appealed.

We, therefore, conclude that it is inelegant and incongruous for the ICJ to hold the Kings and Chiefs of Old Calabar as incompetent to conclude the 1884 Treaty, and turn round to uphold the 1913 Agreements, founded on the said Treaty, as competent, legal and enforceable. Such equivocation is a bizarre abuse of the *nemo dat* principle, as no one could support something upon nothing and expect it to stand, or to give a title superior to that which one possessed. Accordingly, the Arbitral Tribunal in the *Island of Palmas* case, per Max Huber, divested the US of the sovereignty purportedly ceded to it by Spain over the Island of Palmas. It held, *inter alia*, that "... Spain could not transfer more rights than she herself possessed" (UN Reports of International Arbitral Awards, Vol. II, p. 842). We, most respectfully, submit that

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the whole judicial process in the Cameroon-Nigeria border dispute before the ICJ was a drama of Eurocentrism, a conspiracy among the European powers to divest Nigeria of the Bakassi Peninsula because of the security and

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economic purposes it could serve Europe in general, and their stooge, Cameroon in particular, and dwarf Nigeria's spiraling strength and visibility in the region and beyond.

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